

Evaluation of the UTOPIA Model for Simulating the Size Distribution of Microplastics in the Environment

Rakesh Krishnappan
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Author: Rakesh Krishnappan

Supervisors: Matthew MacLeod and Prado Domercq

Abstract

Microplastics are widespread contaminants with complex environmental behavior, making their fate and transport challenging to predict. This study evaluates the UTOPIA model's ability to simulate observed microplastic size distributions across freshwater, marine, and sediment environments. The model was configured using over 50,000 simulation runs to explore a wide range of emission scenarios and parameter combinations, particularly focusing on fragmentation style, fragmentation timescale, and discorporation half-life. Model performance was assessed using RMSE, R^2 , and visual overlay comparisons against observed environmental data from 11 published studies.

Results show that UTOPIA can replicate observed size distributions when input parameters are environmentally plausible. Among the three parameters tested, fragmentation style emerged as the most influential factor affecting model fit, followed by fragmentation timescale. Discorporation half-life was the least important of the three, but sometimes played a secondary role, especially in model scenarios with emissions to terrestrial compartments. Analysis of the top-performing runs revealed clear patterns linking plastic density with specific fragmentation behaviors. Specifically, UTOPIA's modeled size distribution of microplastics agreed best with measurements from the real environment for low-density plastics with faster, erosive fragmentation, and for high-density plastics with slower, more sequential fragmentation.

These findings not only validate the UTOPIA model's structure but also offer recommendations for selecting default input parameters in data-scarce situations. This work contributes to reducing uncertainty in fate modeling and supports the use of size distribution data to constrain model assumptions about microplastic degradation processes.

Keywords:

Microplastics, Size distribution, UTOPIA model, Power law, Fragmentation style, Fragmentation timescale, and Discorporation half-life, Explosive and Erosive fragmentation, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

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Introduction

Microplastics are solid plastic particles, generally less than 5mm in size, that are water-insoluble (Bergmann et al., 2015). Microplastics are composed of a mixture of polymers and chemical additives. Their composition evolves as they undergo various stages of weathering when exposed to the natural environment. Over time, microplastics become more complex due to the absorption of chemical contaminants and the formation of biofilms on their surfaces (Burns & Boxall, 2018).

Microplastics have become an increasingly serious environmental issue due to their global distribution, including the most remote and pristine environments. Their ubiquity results from their dispersion through atmospheric transport, ocean currents, and river systems, leading to widespread contamination even in areas far from direct human activities (Bergmann et al., 2017; Cai et al., 2018; Enders et al., 2015; Velis et al. 2022). This pervasive presence highlights the complexity and severity of microplastic pollution, underlining the urgent need for enhanced understanding, management, and mitigation strategies. Additionally, variations in sampling methods, detection limits, and analytical techniques, lead to challenges in accurately assessing their distribution and impact (Kooi & Koelmans, 2019).

Microplastics are broadly categorized into primary and secondary microplastics. Primary microplastics are intentionally manufactured in 5mm-or-smaller sizes for applications such as cosmetics, personal care products, and industrial abrasives. Primary microplastics particles enter the environment through household sewage discharge, spillage of plastic resin powders or pellets used in air blasting, and the land application of sewage sludge, which may contain synthetic fibers and sedimented microplastics from domestic sources (Gregory, 1996; Horton et al., 2017b).

In contrast, secondary microplastics are generated through the environmental breakdown of larger plastic debris due to UV radiation, mechanical abrasion, biological activity, and temperature changes (Erni-Cassola et al., 2017; Isobe et al., 2014). These particles are a major contributor to environmental microplastic pollution, given the high volume of macroplastic waste already present in ecosystems (Duis and Coors, 2016). Secondary microplastics are introduced to the environment via anthropogenic activities such as littering, waste mismanagement, surface runoff, and soil erosion. Road traffic is another source, with tire and road wear particles (TRWP) being transported by stormwater runoff into surface waters (Kole et al., 2017). A significant share of secondary microplastics in wastewater consists of synthetic fibers released during the washing of synthetic textiles such as polyester, acrylic, and polyamide, with studies estimating up to 1900 fibers may be shed per garment per wash (Browne et al., 2011). These fibers, though often originating from manufactured products, are considered secondary due to their release via physical degradation processes such as wear and laundering. Furthermore, airborne microplastics-including synthetic fibers from clothing, artificial turf, and waste incineration can be mobilized, particularly in urban areas, and later deposited into remote terrestrial or aquatic environments (Dris et al., 2016; Cai et al., 2017). The distribution of microplastics across environmental compartments is heavily influenced by climatic and physical forces such as wind, surface runoff, tides, and flooding, which govern their movement between terrestrial, freshwater, and marine systems (Zhang, 2017).

Conceptually, fragmentation of plastic debris could occur via two bounding pathways that can be thought of as “explosive” and “erosive” fragmentation. In explosive fragmentation there is sudden breakage in the bulk of the plastic particle caused by mechanical stress, rapid environmental fluctuations, or physical collisions. Explosive fragmentation results in relatively large fragments initially, which subsequently undergo further fragmentation processes. In contrast, erosive fragmentation is a gradual process of continuous surface abrasion of very small particles driven by environmental forces such as wind, wave action, and sediment abrasion, which progressively reduces the size of the parent particles over extended periods (Kooi & Koelmans, 2019). It is likely that fragmentation in the environment occurs by some blend of explosive-like and erosive-like pathways, and, importantly, the rate at which fragmentation occurs under natural conditions is still not well understood (Eerkes-Medrano and Thompson, 2018).

Microplastics exhibit various shapes including fragments, spheres, fibers, films, and foams (*Figure 1*). Fragments primarily originate from the degradation of larger plastics, spheres typically represent industrial pellets or cosmetic beads, fibers mostly derive from synthetic textiles, films are generally sourced from packaging materials, and foams result from polystyrene-based insulation or packaging (Imhof et al., 2016; Eo et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Types of shape exhibited by microplastics. Source: Kooi & Koelmans, 2019.

Furthermore, microplastics exist in multiple aggregation states: free-floating, hetero-aggregated with other particulate matter, colonized by microbial communities (biofouled), and combinations thereof (biofouled and hetero-aggregated) (*Figure 2*). These aggregation states significantly influence their distribution, buoyancy, and transport mechanisms within aquatic systems (Enders et al., 2015; Isobe et al., 2015).

Figure 2 Multiple aggregation state of microplastics. Source: GitHub UTOPIA model

Recent studies emphasize the critical influence of size and aggregation state on their environmental fate and ecological implications of microplastics (Ivar do Sul and Costa, 2014; Rocha-Santos and Duarte, 2014). Particularly, smaller microplastics (less than 300 μm) are more abundant and have a higher potential for ingestion by aquatic organisms, consequently entering food webs and causing potential toxicological impacts due to adsorbed chemicals and additives (Cai et al., 2018; Imhof et al., 2016). Microplastics are increasingly recognized as pervasive environmental pollutants present in diverse ecosystems worldwide. Their widespread occurrence has been documented through numerous studies indicating their presence in marine environments, freshwater systems, sediments, and even remote regions such as Arctic deep-sea sediments (Bergmann et al., 2017; Cai et al., 2018; Enders et al., 2015).

To overcome challenges associated with studying microplastics, mathematical models have potential to be effective tools to understand and predict their environmental fate and transport processes. Models provide a structured approach to integrate complex environmental processes,

such as fragmentation, aggregation, biofouling, and settling. Such models facilitate hypothesis generation, scenario analyses, and risk assessments by simulating various environmental conditions and plastic characteristics (Domercq et al., 2022).

A notable example of such modelling efforts is the Full Multi framework, an open-source model specifically developed to study the fate and transport of nano- and microplastics in aquatic systems. The Full Multi framework accounts for fragmentation into predefined size classes, speciation of microplastics (pristine, hetero-aggregated, biofouled, and combinations thereof), dynamic vertical exchanges between water layers and sediments, and horizontal transport by eddy diffusion and advective flow. By integrating these multiple factors, the Full Multi framework enables comprehensive scenario analyses, identification of dominant fate processes, and supports effective environmental management decisions (Domercq et al., 2022).

The UTOPIA model, employed in this research, is an evaluative unit world model that expands on the Full Multi framework to simulate the fate of microplastics in a regional environment. UTOPIA integrates the transport and transformation of microplastics across multiple environmental compartments including air, open ocean, coastal zones, beaches, and soils. The model categorizes microplastics into five distinct size classes (represented by size bins with medians of 0.5, 5, 50, 500, and 5000 μm) and four aggregation states (pristine, hetero-aggregated, biofouled, and biofouled & hetero-aggregated).

Through solving a comprehensive set of mass balance equations, UTOPIA calculates steady-state concentrations of microplastics, facilitating scenario analysis and providing exposure metrics such as overall persistence, characteristic travel distance, and potential transport to remote or targeted locations.

This research is focused on modeling the size distributions of microplastics that have been observed in various environmental matrices, particularly in freshwater, ocean water, and sediments. These observed distributions provide empirical data from the real environment that serves as a benchmark for evaluating the performance of UTOPIA. Multiple field studies have reported microplastic levels in these environmental compartments, often providing detailed data on particle sizes, shapes, and concentrations.

A cornerstone of this research is the study by Kooi and Koelmans (2019), which proposes simplifying the complexity of microplastic characterization using continuous probability distributions. They introduce a three-dimensional (3D) probabilistic framework to describe microplastics based on their size, shape, and density. This approach addresses the limitations of discrete classifications and offers a more comprehensive representation of environmental microplastics. Their paper describes the comparison of microplastic size distributions from 11 different studies covering marine, freshwater, and sediment environments, which provides a robust dataset to compare with fate modelling. This dataset is a central input for this research, enabling validation of UTOPIA's simulated size distributions against real-world observations (Kooi & Koelmans, 2019).

By compiling and analyzing size distribution data from key studies that were summarized by Kooi and Koelmans (2019), such as those by Imhof et al. (2016) in Lake Garda, Cai et al. (2018) in the South China Sea, Enders et al. (2015) in the Atlantic Ocean, and Bergmann et al. (2017) in Arctic deep-sea sediments, this thesis establishes a reference dataset for comparison with model outputs. These data reflect the diversity and complexity of microplastic pollution under varying environmental conditions and sampling methods. By systematically comparing

UTOPIA's output against these observed size distributions, this study aims to identify knowledge gaps, validate assumptions, and improve model accuracy in representing real-world conditions.

A major challenge in modelling microplastic fate lies in the profound uncertainties surrounding key transformation processes, namely fragmentation and discorporation, where discorporation refers to degradation of plastic particles into polymer fragments that are too small to retain the properties of a solid. While UTOPIA simulates these mechanisms, there is a striking lack of empirical data, particularly from environmental settings, to guide the selection of appropriate model parameters. Most existing studies are laboratory-based and do not fully capture the complexity of real-world conditions. As a result, critical input parameters such as fragmentation style (i.e., explosive, erosive, or mixed), fragmentation timescale, and discorporation half-life are poorly constrained. This introduces a significant degree of uncertainty in predicting the environmental fate and size distribution of microplastics.

This research aims to address these uncertainties by explicitly testing a core hypothesis, i.e., that **fitting the UTOPIA model to observed environmental size distributions will constrain assumptions and uncertainties about fragmentation patterns and timescales for fragmentation and discorporation half-life**. Rather than simply demonstrating that the model can replicate observed distributions, an outcome that can sometimes result from implausible parameter combinations, this study focuses on identifying scenarios that are both environmentally reasonable (in terms of emission sources, plastic density, and receiving compartments) and provide strong agreement with measured data. Through this approach, the research not only assesses the performance and limitations of the UTOPIA model but also identifies robust parameter combinations that can be a starting point for realistic simulations. The results are expected to narrow uncertainty, improve the predictive power of fate models, and support more targeted environmental management of microplastic pollution.

Theory and Method

Power Law Distribution in Environment

A growing body of research demonstrates that microplastic size distributions in the environment often follow a power law distribution, where the number of particles decreases linearly as particle size increases when plotted on a log-log scale. This statistical relationship has been widely applied to characterize particle size distributions (PSDs) in environmental studies, especially in marine and estuarine systems. The power law distribution is generally represented by equation (1).

$$\log(y) = \log(b) - a\log(x) \quad \dots (1)$$

where x is the particle size in its longest dimension and y is the abundance.

In a comparative study across estuarine and oceanic environments, Buonassissi and Dierssen (2010) observed that power law distributions provided a good fit for particle size spectra from 6 to 250 μm . Their analysis found PSD slopes typically ranged between 2.7 and 4.7, with steeper slopes corresponding to regions dominated by finer particles, such as the open ocean. Shallower slopes were characteristic of estuarine environments with higher particle concentrations and larger aggregate formations.

Similarly, Thomas et al. (2016) applied power law and lognormal models to predict the particle size distribution of suspended sediments during stormwater runoff events at construction sites. Their findings confirmed that particle size data in runoff environments often adhere to power law characteristics, particularly for finer fractions. Power law-based formulations proved useful in describing the frequency and relative abundance of different particle size classes.

In the Pearl River Estuary, Feng et al. (2017) examined multimodal PSDs of bottom sediments and decomposed them into lognormal subpopulations. While their primary focus was on sediment stability, their analysis also showed that particle populations in coastal environments exhibit distribution patterns consistent with power law or lognormal behavior. These findings suggest that power law approximations can be applied beyond suspended particles, extending to bed sediments.

Kooi and Koelmans (2019) demonstrated the relevance of power law distributions in characterizing microplastics. In their study, they fitted power law curves to empirical data from 11 studies that reported a total of 19 datasets that presented results in at least 10 size bins within the microplastic range (*Figure 3*). Their analysis yielded an average exponent $\alpha = 1.6 \pm 0.5$ ($n = 19$), indicating that microplastic distributions exhibit heavy tails and scale-free properties typical of fragmentation processes. Their work also emphasized that deviations at the lower and upper size ends may arise from sampling limitations and analytical detection limits.

Fitting size distribution data with the power law distribution thus provides an efficient and empirically supported method to describe the wide-ranging and scale-free nature of environmental microplastic distributions.

Figure 3: Relative microplastic abundance for different particle sizes. Source: Kooi & Koelmans, 2019

Microplastic Size Distribution and Sampling Methods

Microplastics in the environment exhibit a wide range of sizes, typically spanning from tens of micrometers to a few millimeters. Across diverse ecosystems, from freshwater to marine environments and sediments, studies consistently report that smaller microplastic particles are more abundant than larger ones. This trend is largely attributed to the fragmentation of larger plastic items and the environmental mobility of finer particles (Cai et al., 2018; Enders et al., 2015; Imhof et al., 2016; Bergmann et al., 2017).

Sampling methods for microplastics vary depending on the environmental matrix and often determine the lower size detection limit in the specific matrix. For example, surface waters are commonly sampled using nets (e.g., manta or neuston nets) with mesh sizes typically $\geq 300 \mu\text{m}$, although these methods can miss finer particles (Isobe et al., 2014; Erni-Cassola et al., 2017). To address this, pump filtration systems are increasingly employed to capture microplastics down to $20 \mu\text{m}$ or smaller (Cai et al., 2018; Enders et al., 2015). In sediments, grab samplers and box corers are widely used, allowing for depth-specific collection of particles (Imhof et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2019).

Once collected, microplastic samples typically undergo density separation, filtration, and organic matter removal using chemical digestion. Analytical techniques such as Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and Raman micro spectroscopy are standard tools for identifying polymer types and confirming particle characteristics (Imhof et al., 2016; Cai et al., 2018). Additionally, Nile Red staining followed by fluorescence microscopy has emerged as a rapid detection method for identifying microplastics, particularly those below 100 μm (Erni-Cassola et al., 2017).

Despite variations in methodologies, a consistent finding across studies is the dominance of smaller microplastics (<500 μm) in most environments. For example, Cai et al. (2018) found that 92% of microplastics in South China Sea samples were <300 μm , while Imhof et al. (2016) reported that particles in Lake Garda peaked around 130 μm . Bergmann et al. (2017) observed that ~80% of Arctic sediment microplastics were ≤ 25 μm , and Zhang et al. (2019) found that over half of sediment microplastics in Sishili Bay were <500 μm .

These general patterns emphasize the need for high-resolution sampling and detection techniques and highlight the importance of incorporating realistic size distributions into environmental fate models such as UTOPIA. The complexity of environmental microplastic distributions and underscore the importance of robust sampling and analysis techniques. These observed distributions and methodological insights serve as vital references for evaluating and improving model performance in simulating the fate of microplastics across environmental compartments.

Observed Environmental Size Distributions of microplastic

To benchmark the performance of the UTOPIA model, this study compiles and analyzes observed microplastic size distributions from various environmental contexts from published datasets. Following Kooi and Koelmans (2019), the selection criteria included studies reporting particle size distributions in at least 10 size bins, collected from surface water, deep water, or sediment samples. Key information such as sampling location, environmental matrix, method, and dominant polymer types was documented.

In the Fram Strait (Arctic), Bergmann et al. (2017), working with sediment cores (sediment matrix), found that nearly 80% of microplastic particles were ≤ 25 μm , predominantly consisting of polyethylene (PE) and polyester (PES). The microplastics were collected using sediment coring, and particle identification was carried out through FTIR analysis.

Cai et al. (2018) conducted sampling in the South China Sea using pump filtration and reported that 92% of particles were <300 μm . Dominant plastic types included PE, polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS). Enders et al. (2015) similarly used pump-based sampling in the Atlantic Ocean and observed high abundances of particles <100 μm , with fragments and fibers being the most prevalent forms.

Eo et al. (2019) collected microplastics from the Nakdong River in South Korea using grab sampling in water and sediments. PE and PP were dominant in both matrices, with fibers being particularly prevalent. In the Plymouth Sound, U.K., Erni-Cassola et al. (2017) used a net tow method to collect surface water samples and applied Nile Red staining for particle detection. Their study reported a broad range of particle sizes with notable abundance below 100 μm .

Imhof et al. (2016) studied sediment cores from Lake Garda, Italy, and found the most frequent particle size to be around 130 μm . Fragments, fibers, and films were commonly identified, with PE and PES as the dominant polymers.

In the Seto Inland Sea, Japan, Isobe et al. (2014) used neuston nets and FTIR to identify microplastics, which were mostly composed of PE and ranged from 100-2000 μm in size. Their follow-up study in the East Asian Seas (Isobe et al., 2015) reaffirmed PE and PP as the major components across regional waters.

Song et al. (2018) sampled water from Korean coastal and offshore zones using grab and pump methods, detecting particles primarily in the 50-500 μm range. Common polymers included PE, PP, and PET. Finally, Zhang et al. (2019) analyzed sediment samples from Sishili Bay in the Yellow Sea using box coring and reported that more than half the particles were <500 μm , with PE, PVC, and PP being the most common polymers.

After compiling these datasets, a standardized filtering process was applied to ensure consistency and reliability in evaluating UTOPIA model outputs. The following criteria were used to refine the dataset:

1. Zero-abundance exclusions: Observations with zero abundance (% , count, or count/ m^3) were excluded since log transformation is not applicable to zero values.
2. Trendline shape validation: Only datasets where the maximum abundance corresponded to the smallest reported size were included. Studies showing a decline at small size classes were excluded due to likely sampling or analytical limitations.
3. Detection limit check: The maximum valid size in each dataset was assessed based on a theoretical particle detection limit (PDL), excluding size ranges that exceeded realistic detection thresholds.

These studies serve as essential references for evaluating the UTOPIA model by offering real-world distributions that reflect a range of environmental conditions, sampling techniques, and polymer compositions.

UTOPIA Model

UTOPIA is an open-source, multimedia mass-balance model developed to simulate the environmental fate of microplastics. The program is written in Python and was run in this study with version 3.10.5. UTOPIA describes a unit-world environment of 17 interconnected compartments representing aquatic, atmospheric, terrestrial, and coastal systems. The model tracks plastic particles in five microplastic size bins: 0.5, 5, 50, 500, and 5000 μm , and four aggregation states: pristine, hetero-aggregated, biofouled, and biofouled & hetero-aggregated.

UTOPIA solves a system of 340 coupled first-order differential equations, enabling the calculation of steady-state concentrations of microplastics in terms of mass (g) and particle number (N) across all environmental compartments, size fractions and aggregation states. The model outputs key exposure metrics such as overall persistence, characteristic travel distance, and transfer efficiency, which are useful for comparative assessment of the long-range transport potential and environmental exposure caused by microplastics.

The UTOPIA model builds on earlier work from the Nano2Plast project and incorporates aquatic processes from the Full Multi model. It extends this framework by including non-

aquatic processes such as sea spray aerosol resuspension, soil-air exchanges, and deposition pathways (wet and dry). Emission scenarios, fragmentation patterns (explosive vs. erosive), and environmental conditions can be adjusted to simulate a range of real-world scenarios.

Parameterization in the UTOPIA model involves several steps. First, the user selects input parameters that define the properties of the plastic. These include the density of the plastic material and the specific composition of the microplastic particles being modelled.

Second, weathering processes such as degradation and fragmentation are specified. There are three main parameters in the model which are as follows:

1. **Fragmentation timescale:** Fragmentation timescale determines how quickly microplastics physically break down into smaller particles. In UTOPIA, this can be user-defined or set to a default half-time of 36.5 days for the largest size fraction of free particles in surface water, based on estimates from Domercq et al. (2021). The model adjusts this rate based on particle aggregation state and compartment type and depth. Hetero-aggregated microplastics are assumed to fragment 100 times more slowly than free particles, biofouled free particles fragment two times slower than free ones, while biofouled & hetero-aggregated particles fragment at a rate two times slower than hetero-aggregated ones. Fragmentation in the lower water compartments and in the surface of the soil compartments is 10 times slower than in the surface water compartments. These assumptions allow UTOPIA to simulate how environmental aging and aggregation influence the persistence and transformation of microplastics.
2. **Fragmentation Style:** Fragmentation style in UTOPIA is controlled by the fragmentation index (FI), a parameter ranging from 0 to 1 that describes how particles fragment into smaller size classes. An FI value of 0 corresponds to erosive fragmentation, in which particle surfaces gradually shed small fragments. An FI of 1 represents sequential or explosive fragmentation, where particles break abruptly and completely into the next smaller size class. Intermediate FI values represent blended fragmentation behaviors and can be used to simulate a spectrum of real-world fragmentation processes.

Fragmentation is implemented through a fragment size distribution (fsd) matrix, where each row defines the fraction of mass from a parent size class redistributed into smaller bins upon fragmentation. The smallest size bin is assumed not to fragment further, and its row in the matrix is filled with zeros. (Domercq et al. (2024)).

Erosive Fragmentation (FI = 0)

Most of the mass remains in the same size class, with a small portion transferred to smaller bins.

[[0, 0, 0, 0, 0],
 [1, 0, 0, 0, 0],
 [0.99, 0.01, 0, 0, 0],
 [0.999, 0, 0.001, 0, 0],
 [0.9999, 0, 0, 0.0001, 0]]

Sequential fragmentation (FI = 1)

All the mass from a size class moves directly into the next smaller size bin.

[[0, 0, 0, 0, 0],
 [1, 0, 0, 0, 0],
 [0, 1, 0, 0, 0],
 [0, 0, 1, 0, 0],
 [0, 0, 0, 1, 0]]

3. **Discorporation half-life:** Discorporation refers to the chemical or biological breakdown of microplastics into non-plastic residues. In UTOPIA, users can define a custom discorporation half-life (`thalf_deg`) for free microplastics in surface water or use a default value of 66,000 days (Domercq et al., 2021). Aggregation state influences discorporation as well: hetero-aggregated particles degrade 10 times slower than the default value, while biofouled particles degrade twice as fast as the default value, under the assumption that some colonizing microbes are capable of excreting enzymes that cause polymer degradation. These rates are further modified by compartment: in surface water, both fragmentation and degradation occur most rapidly, but they are 10 times slower in deep water and soil surface compartments, and 100 times slower in sediments and deeper soils. This framework enables the model to reflect the compartment-specific persistence of microplastics under various environmental conditions.

Third, the user defines the emission scenario. This involves choosing the input flow in grams per second and specifying the size, form, and target environmental compartment for the microplastic emissions. Available size fractions include 0.5, 5, 50, 500, and 5000 μm . Microplastic forms include free, hetero-aggregated, biofouled, and biofouled & hetero-aggregated. Emission compartments can be specified as any of the 17 compartments in the UTOPIA environment, i.e., surface and subsurface aquatic, terrestrial, and atmospheric environments, such as ocean surface water, sediments, soils, and air.

The model output provides several key results that are essential for interpreting the fate and behavior of microplastics in the environment. These include a comprehensive model run summary, mass and particle number concentrations as well as mass and particle number fractions visualized through distribution heatmaps for each compartment, size fraction and microplastic form.

Configuring UTOPIA Model for observed size distribution Validation

The complete UTOPIA model was executed for each scenario, however most results reported in this thesis were generated from only the section of the program responsible for calculating the mass and particle number distribution across compartments and size fractions. This part of the model result was isolated from sections that produce default data visualizations to enable more rapid model run times.

In the database of observed microplastic size distributions, it was noted that the percentage of particles smaller than the 5 μm size bin was zero in nearly all cases, likely reflecting a lack of analytical capabilities to detect and quantify the smallest microplastics. As a result, although all five size bins were simulated in the model, only the results for the 50 μm , 500 μm , and 5000 μm bins were retained for analysis.

From the filtered size bins, the relative abundance of microplastics in the 3 size bins was calculated for each compartment. This was done by dividing the number of particles in each size bin by the total number of particles within the three largest size bins in that compartment. The calculation was repeated across all three selected size bins and for every environmental compartment represented in the model. This relative abundance data was then fit with a power law distribution using the logarithmic values of both the relative abundance and the size fraction. All scripts used to configure and run UTOPIA simulations for this study—including

parameter looping, size distribution comparison, and data formatting—are available at (Domercq et al., 2021).

Each of the 11 studies was matched to the most representative compartments in the UTOPIA model, which would reflect the “target” model compartment that represents the locations of microplastics that were analyzed in the study. The selection of compartments was based on the environmental matrix reported in the original studies, such as sediment, surface water, or deeper aquatic layers. This alignment ensures that the comparison between observed and simulated size distributions is both meaningful and environmentally relevant. In addition to compartment matching, the most appropriate emission scenarios were selected to reflect the likely sources of microplastic pollution in each study context. The full set of study-compartment and emission scenario pairings is provided in Table 1.

Parameter Variation for Scenario Simulation

The current version of UTOPIA is parameterized only for spherical microplastic particles, so all scenarios in this study assume spherical particle shapes. The other four input parameters required to run the model are plastic particle density, fragmentation style (FI), Discorporation half time (thalf_deg), and fragmentation timescale (thalf_frag). These parameters were therefore considered for scenario simulations as they are expected to have a high impact on microplastic fragmentation, transport, and persistence across environmental compartments. In each simulation, emissions were defined as pristine (unbiofouled, unaggregated) microplastics released entirely in the largest size class (5000 μm).

The values of each input considered in the scenarios are:

1. Plastic density (mpdensity): [900, 1100, 1500] kg/m^3
2. Fragmentation style (FI): [0, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0] - ranging from more erosive to more explosive fragmentation
3. Discorporation half time (thalf_deg): [316, 1000, 10000, 31600, 100000] days
4. Fragmentation timescale (thalf_frag): [10, 31.6, 100, 316] days

A looping routine was created to run all ($3 \times 5 \times 5 \times 4 = 300$) possible combinations of these parameter values for a given emission compartments and target compartments. All other model parameters were kept at their default values. By systematically varying each of these parameters, the study aims to understand their influence on model outputs, evaluate how they affected the predicted size distributions under different environmental scenarios, and identify combinations of input parameters that lead to good agreement with size distributions of microplastic that are observed in the environment.

Comparison of Observed and Modelled Size Distributions

For each iteration of the parameter loop, a size distribution plot was generated using the logarithmic values of relative abundance and size bins and saved under a unique name. The observed environmental size distribution from the corresponding dataset was then overlaid on the modelled output. This comparison was conducted using the matched compartments and emission scenarios outlined in Table 1.

Each scenario was evaluated both visually by inspecting how well the overlay aligned with each other and quantitatively, the following three methods were used to evaluate the overlay fitness.

Table 1: Selection of environmentally plausible target compartment and emission compartment for each study/dataset

Paper	Location	Selected Plausible Target Compartments	Selected Plausible Emission Compartments
Bergmann et al., 2017	Sediment samples collected from Fram Strait, Arctic Ocean	Sediment_Ocean: As the study sampled deep-sea sediment. Sediment_Coast: Comparison with coastal transport sources.	Ocean_Surface_Water: Major transport source & settle over time Coast_Surface_Water & Coast_Column_Water: Potential sources from melting sea ice and coastal erosion.
Cai et al., 2018	South China Sea (Pearl River Estuary and offshore areas) surface to a 200-meter depth	Surface_Freshwater: This aligns with MP originating from the river. Coast_Surface_Water: Tracks MP near the estuary. Ocean_Surface_Water: Matches the MP distribution in the study. Ocean_Column_Water: MPs were also detected down to 200m deep.	Surface_Freshwater: River discharge was a primary MP source. Urban_Soil: Industrial sources in coastal cities contributed MPs. Coast_Surface_Water: Major accumulation points for microplastics from land-based sources before drifting offshore.
Enders et al., 2015	Sampled from Surface and Mixed Layer in Atlantic Ocean	Ocean_Surface_Water: Plastics were sampled from surface waters. Ocean_Mixed_Water: Wind-induced mixing affects distribution.	Ocean_Surface_Water: Dominant source as plastics found floating. Coast_Surface_Water: Coastal waters contribute plastic inputs.
Eo et al., 2019	Samples from surface water, water column & sediments	Surface_Freshwater & Bulk_Freshwater: Main pathway for MP. Sediment_Freshwater: Matches deposited plastics in riverbeds	Urban_Soil: Plastics from cities and wastewater. Surface_Freshwater: Riverine transport is dominant.
Erni-Cassola et al., 2017	Sea surface samples Plymouth Sound, U.K.	Coast_Surface_Water: Study focuses on a coastal marine system. Ocean_Surface_Water: Some plastics were observed offshore.	Coast_Surface_Water: Major input from coastal activities. Urban_Soil_Surface: Potential land-based inputs.
Imhof et al., 2016	Samples collected from lake sediments and shorelines.	Sediment_Freshwater: Best match since plastics are sampled in lake sediments.	Surface_Freshwater: Inputs from runoff and urban waste.
Isobe et al., 2014	Samples from river mouths, coastal waters & offshore.	Coast_Surface_Water: Initial plastic accumulation. Ocean_Surface_Water: Plastics transported offshore.	Surface_Freshwater: Riverine transport from land to sea. Coast_Surface_Water: Nearshore accumulation before offshore transport.
Isobe et al., 2015	Samples collected from Ocean Seawater, East Asian Seas	Ocean_Surface_Water: Matches surface water sampling. Ocean_Mixed_Water: Accounts for wind-driven mixing.	Coast_Surface_Water: Major sources from China, Korea, and Japan. Air – Potential atmospheric deposition.
Scheurer et al., 2018	29 sites in Swiss floodplain soils across nature reserves.	Background_Soil_Surface: Represents floodplain deposition. Agricultural_Soil_Surface: Potential terrestrial input sources.	Urban_Soil_Surface: Plastic waste from urban areas.
Song et al., 2018	Surface water (0–0.2 m) and water column (3–58 m depth)	Ocean_Surface_Water: Plastics at surface layers. Ocean_Column_Water: Represents water column transport.	Urban_Soil_Surface: Inputs from urban runoff. Surface_Freshwater: River discharges.
Zhang et al., 2019	28 sediment stations at depths of 4–24 meters.	Sediment_Ocean: Matches seabed sediment sampling. Sediment_Coast: Nearshore influences.	Coast_Surface_Water: Inputs from nearshore sources. Surface_Freshwater: Riverine transport.

1. Slope and Intercept Comparison with Euclidean Distance: Linear trendlines were fitted to both observed and modelled plots. The Euclidean distance between their slopes and intercept was calculated to evaluate similarity. A lower Euclidean distance indicates a closer match.

$$D = \sqrt{((m_1 - m_2)^2 + (b_1 - b_2)^2)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where m_1 , b_1 and m_2 , b_2 are the slopes and intercepts of the observed and modelled trendlines, respectively.

2. R-squared (R²) Comparison: To assess how well the model reproduced the shape of observed microplastic size distributions, R² (coefficient of determination) was calculated. Because UTOPIA outputs relative abundances for only three predefined size bins (50, 500, and 5000 μm), a direct bin-by-bin comparison with observed data, which typically includes more size bins, was not possible.

Instead, the power law function was fitted to the modelled data from the three UTOPIA bins. This fitted curve was then used to estimate relative abundances at the size bins reported in the observed dataset.

The R² was calculated by comparing these power law-predicted values to the actual observed log-transformed relative abundances using equation 3.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where y_i : log (relative abundance) in the observed dataset at bin i , \hat{y}_i : model-predicted log (relative abundance) using the power law and \bar{y} : mean of the observed log (relative abundance) values.

A higher R² indicates better alignment between the modelled power-law prediction and the observed size distribution.

3. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE): RMSE was calculated between the observed and modelled values. A lower RMSE indicates a better match between datasets.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(y_{i_obs} - y_{i_mod})^2}{n}} \quad \dots (4)$$

RMSE was used to quantify the difference between observed and modelled size distributions. Since the UTOPIA model outputs mass and particle number concentrations for only three size bins (50 μm , 500 μm , and 5000 μm), while the observed datasets typically contain 10 or more size bins, direct comparison was not possible. To address this, a power law was fitted to the model output using Equation (1), allowing the simulation results to be interpolated into a continuous size distribution. Relative abundances were then calculated across the same bin ranges as the observed data, enabling a standardized comparison. RMSE was then computed based on these aligned distributions, with lower values indicating a closer fit between the model and observations.

Among the three methods, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was selected as the preferred metric for evaluating the fitness of the agreement between modelled and observed size distributions. Its ability to quantify the average deviation across all size bins made it a robust and interpretable indicator of model performance.

However, it was observed that although the RMSE values indicated a good fit between modelled and observed data, in some cases the modelled distributions did not follow a clear power law pattern. While the linear trendline provided a reasonable match, the underlying three data points did not follow a power law distribution, usually because the relative abundance in the smallest (50 μm) size bin was lower than the relative abundance in the next largest (500 μm) size bin.

To address this, the Spearman rank correlation coefficient was introduced as an additional filter. This non-parametric measure was used to identify linear regressions with a monotonic relationship between particle size and relative abundance. If the Spearman rank correlation coefficient for the modelled data was less than 1, the dataset was excluded from the comparison results. This ensured that only those modelled distributions that both aligned well with observed data and exhibited power law characteristics were included in the final analysis.

Post-Processing of Model Results for Comparative Analysis

The raw output of the model, along with the corresponding comparison to observed data, was exported to an Excel file. This file was then imported into a separate Excel workbook for further processing and data analysis using Microsoft Power Query. Through this interface, all necessary filters were applied.

For better clarity and comparison, a separate Excel file was created for each observed study and its corresponding model output. The data within each file was sorted in decreasing order of RMSE value, enabling the best-fitting simulation results to appear at the top. In addition to the numerical data, plots from each iteration were linked directly to the corresponding data entries, allowing for seamless visual inspection of model performance. The complete set of processed UTOPIA model outputs, including filtered results, overlay plots, and comparisons of model data to observed datasets, is provided as supplementary material ([Supplementary File S1](#)).

Z-Score Standardization and Parameter Influence Analysis

Z-score standardization is a statistical technique used to compare variables that have different units, scales, or ranges. It transforms each value in a dataset to indicate how many standard deviations it is from the mean of that dataset. The Z-score is calculated using the formula:

$$Z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad \dots (5)$$

Where x is the individual data point, μ is the mean of the dataset, and σ is the standard deviation.

To enable a consistent and non-parametric comparison across input parameters and model outcomes, Z-score standardization was applied to the model inputs, fragmentation style (FI), discorporation half time (`thalf_deg`), and fragmentation timescale (`thalf_frag`), and the model performance metric, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). This allowed all variables to be placed on the same scale and facilitated direct comparison of their relative influence. By standardizing RMSE, the analysis could evaluate whether deviations in input parameters corresponded to relatively better or worse models fit, independent of absolute error magnitudes. To interpret the effects of each parameter on model fit, multiple linear regression analysis was performed using the standardized RMSE as the dependent variable. This statistical technique enabled the quantification of the strength and direction of influence of each input parameter on modeled

RMSE compared to observations while accounting for potential interactions and correlations between parameters

The combined approach of standardization and regression provided a robust framework for identifying which parameters had the most significant impact on the agreement of modelled microplastic size distributions with empirical observations from the real environment.

To consider all plausible combinations of emission compartment, target compartment and microplastic particle property scenarios, and after filtering results to remove non-power law size distributions from the model outputs, a total of 21,341 model runs were included in the initial analysis. To better understand how each input parameter influenced model performance (as measured by standardized RMSE), we isolated specific conditions across the dataset. In order to reduce the influence of contextual variability and isolate the effects of the input parameters, four key factors were held constant during subset selection: Observed dataset (i.e., study), Target compartment, Receiving compartment and plastic density.

By fixing these contextual variables, we ensured that comparisons were being made between model runs operating under the same environmental assumptions, differing only in the key input parameters of interest: fragmentation style (FI), discorporation half-life (thalf_deg), and fragmentation timescale (thalf_frag).

From this filtering process, a total of 392 unique model subsets were generated that represent plausible emission and target compartments for one of the empirical datasets, and a constant plastic density. Within each subset, Z-score standardization was applied to all variables, including the RMSE, enabling consistent and scale-free comparisons of the relative importance of FI, thalf_deg and thalf_frag in determining agreement between the model and the empirical observations.

Multiple linear regression was then performed independently for each of the 392 scenarios, using standardized RMSE as the dependent variable and the standardized input parameters (FI, thalf_deg, thalf_frag) as predictors. This approach allowed for quantification of:

1. The relative importance of each parameter in influencing model results.
2. The directionality of each effect (i.e., whether increases in a parameter tended to increase or reduce RMSE).
3. The robustness of these effects across diverse environmental scenarios and datasets.

The regression outputs across subsets provided a detailed map of parameter influence under a wide range of emission source compartment and target compartment scenarios. These results helped identify which parameters consistently had the greatest impact on model fit and offered insights into potential parameter prioritization when optimizing microplastic fate simulations using the UTOPIA model.

Results

In total, this study involved over 50,000 simulation runs using the UTOPIA model, systematically exploring a broad range of environmental conditions, parameter combinations, and emission-to-compartment scenarios influencing the fate of microplastics. These extensive simulations enabled a robust comparison between modelled outcomes and observed environmental data across various aquatic and sedimentary systems.

Numerous scenarios yielded excellent agreement between observed and modelled microplastic size distributions. In many cases, specific parameter combinations produced strong alignment with observed trends, as demonstrated by low RMSE values, high R^2 values, and power law curves that closely matched the slope and curvature of the observed distributions. These outcomes indicate that the model is capable of replicating not only the general shape of environmental size distributions but also the relative abundance trends across a broad size range.

To systematically highlight the most successful simulations, the best two model runs (based on lowest RMSE) for each dataset are summarized in Table 2, where key input parameters such as plastic density, fragmentation style, degradation half-life, and fragmentation timescale are listed for each top-performing scenario. These results reflect not just statistical fit, but also environmentally plausible parameter choices such as buoyant plastics remaining in surface waters, or denser plastics showing delayed fragmentation in deeper compartments. Additionally, Figure 4 presents selected overlay plots from these best-fitting scenarios, visually illustrating the degree of agreement between observed and modelled size distributions.

Figure 4: Examples for Overlay Plots of Observed and Modelled Microplastic Size Distributions for Best-Fit Scenarios

Table 2: Summary of Model Runs with Observed Data: Top Two Best-Fit Scenarios Based on RMSE

Observed Dataset	Target Compartment	R-squared	RMSE	Density (kg/m3)	Emission compartment	FI	thalf_deg	thalf_frag
Sea Surface Fibers Song	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.85	0.12	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.7	1000	31.6
Sea Surface Fibers Song	Coast_Surface_Water	0.85	0.12	900	Surface_Freshwater	0.3	10000	10
Fragments in water Eo	Bulk_Freshwater	0.95	0.16	900	Surface_Freshwater	0.3	31600	10
Fragments in water Eo	Bulk_Freshwater	0.94	0.16	900	Surface_Freshwater	0.3	10000	31.6
Sea Surface Fragments Song	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.94	0.18	900	Impacted_Soil_Surface	0.5	100000	31.6
Sea Surface Fragments Song	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.94	0.18	900	Impacted_Soil_Surface	0.5	100000	100
Sea Surface all Isobe L3	Coast_Surface_Water	0.57	0.19	900	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.5	31600	31.6
Sea Surface all Isobe L3	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.56	0.19	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.5	10000	100
Fresh water sediments Imhof	Sediment_Freshwater	0.68	0.18	1100	Surface_Freshwater	0.3	316	10
Fresh water sediments Imhof	Sediment_Freshwater	0.68	0.18	1500	Surface_Freshwater	0.3	316	10
Sea Surface all Cai	Surface_Freshwater	0.92	0.17	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.3	1000	10
Sea Surface all Cai	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.92	0.17	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.5	1000	10
Sea Surface Fibers Enders	Ocean_Surface_Water	0.77	0.19	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.3	1000	316
Sea Surface Fibers Enders	Coast_Surface_Water	0.77	0.19	900	Coast_Column_Water	0.5	10000	31.6
Fragments in sediment Eo	Sediment_Freshwater	0.84	0.21	1500	Surface_Freshwater	1	100000	10
Fragments in sediment Eo	Sediment_Freshwater	0.84	0.21	1100	Surface_Freshwater	1	100000	10
Sea Sediment Bergmann	Sediment_Ocean	0.96	0.13	1100	Coast_Surface_Water	1	10000	100
Sea Sediment Bergmann	Sediment_Ocean	0.96	0.13	1100	Coast_Surface_Water	1	31600	100
Sea Surface all Erni-Cassola	Coast_Surface_Water	0.76	0.23	1100	Coast_Column_Water	1	100000	316
Sea Surface all Erni-Cassola	Coast_Surface_Water	0.47	0.28	1100	Coast_Column_Water	0.7	316	316
Sea Surface all Zhang	Sediment_Ocean	0.76	0.35	1500	Ocean_Surface_Water	1	100000	316
Sea Surface all Zhang	Sediment_Ocean	0.76	0.35	1100	Ocean_Surface_Water	1	100000	316

Analysis of Top-Performing Parameter Combinations Based on Plastic Density

A focused analysis was conducted on the top 20 best-fitting model results for each observed dataset, selected based on the lowest RMSE values ([Supplementary File S2](#)). These scenarios were further grouped according to plastic density, low-density (900 kg/m³) and high-density (1100–1500 kg/m³) and categorized by ranges of fragmentation style (FI), degradation half-life (t_half_deg), and fragmentation timescale (t_frag_gen). Fragmentation styles were classified into two groups: low (FI = 0.3–0.5), representing more erosive fragmentation, and high (FI = 0.7–1), indicative of sequential or explosive fragmentation. Discorporation half-life were grouped into low (316, 1000, 10000 days) and high (31600, 100000 days), while fragmentation timescales were divided into short (10, 31.6 days) and long (100, 316 days) durations.

For low-density microplastics (900 kg/m³) (*Figure 5*), which are buoyant and common in surface water environments the most frequent and successful parameter combinations were strongly associated with lower fragmentation style values FI (0.3 or 0.5). These occurred in 81% of the top runs for low-density plastic scenarios, suggesting that an erosive type of fragmentation is more likely for low-density plastics. Similarly, most of the cases (143, or 74%) featured shorter fragmentation timescales (10 or 31.6 days), implying that fragmentation into smaller particles occurs more quickly for buoyant plastics, whereas 51 cases (26%) applied longer timescales (100 or 316 days). The distribution of discorporation half-life was very nearly balanced, with 98 cases (51%) using higher discorporation half-life (31600 or 100000 days) and 96 cases (49%) using lower values (316, 1000, or 10000 days), refer *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: Distribution of parameter groupings among top-performing runs for low-density plastics (900 kg/m³)

Scenarios with best agreement with empirical data involving high-density polymers (1100–1500 kg/m³) (*Figure 6*), showed a contrasting pattern. These denser materials were most often (126 out of 166, or 76%), associated with higher fragmentation style values (FI = 0.7–1) in 76% of the best-fitting model runs, suggesting that these plastics are more likely to undergo sudden or sequential fragmentation, while only 40 cases (24%) used lower values (FI = 0.3 or 0.5). Furthermore, 107 cases (64%) of top runs for high-density plastics involved longer fragmentation timescales (100–316 days), consistent with their tendency to sink or settle and persist as larger particles for extended periods before breaking apart. Regarding discorporation half-life, 95 cases (57%) used lower degradation values, while 71 cases (43%) featured higher discorporation half-life, suggesting a slight preference for shorter discorporation durations in high-density plastic scenarios, which is discussed in detail below.

Figure 6: Distribution of parameter groupings among top-performing runs for high-density plastics (1000-1100 kg/m³)

Analysis based on Z Score standardization and Multiple linear regressions

Multiple linear regressions were performed on 392 Z-score standardized datasets, where each dataset represented a unique combination of observational study, emission and target compartments, and plastic density. The standardization allowed direct comparison between input parameters of differing scales by converting them into normalized unitless values, thus enabling meaningful regression analysis. The relationship between each standardized input parameter such as fragmentation style (FI), fragmentation timescale (t_frag), and discorporation half-life (t_half_deg) and the model performance metric (RMSE) was assessed by analyzing the magnitude of the regression coefficients (β). These β -values were categorized as follows: Strong ($|\beta| > 0.5$), Moderate ($0.3 < |\beta| \leq 0.5$), Weak ($0.1 < |\beta| \leq 0.3$), and None ($|\beta| \leq 0.1$). The complete dataset used for Z-score standardization and multiple linear regression analysis, including standardized parameter values and RMSE scores for 392 subsets, is provided in [Supplementary File S3](#).

The analysis revealed that fragmentation style had the most consistently strong relationship with RMSE. Specifically, 56% of the regression models showed a strong correlation between fragmentation style and RMSE, with an additional 10% showing moderate correlation. Only 10% of the cases showed no meaningful relationship, suggesting that the assumed fragmentation pathway (erosive vs. sequential) is often a major driver of the predicted particle size distribution. See *Figure 7* for visual summary.

Figure 7: Influence of RMSE on the input parameters (Fragmentation style, Fragmentation timescale and Discorporation half-life)

Fragmentation timescale showed strong correlation with RMSE in 107 of the 392 regression subsets (27%). A moderate correlation was observed in 191 subsets (49%), while 73 subsets (19%) had a weak correlation. Only 21 subsets (5%) showed no correlation between fragmentation timescale and RMSE, suggesting high influence on RMSE. See *Figure 7* for visual summary.

Discorporation half-life ($t_{\text{half_deg}}$), by contrast, was less impactful across the full dataset. It showed a strong relationship with RMSE in only 22% of the regressions, and no meaningful correlation in 19%, suggesting its effects may be more context dependent.

To evaluate the relative influence of each input parameter on model performance and results, the standardized regression coefficients (β -values) obtained from the multiple linear regressions were compared across all 392 subset analyses. Each subset represented a unique combination of observed dataset, model compartment, receiving compartment, and plastic density.

Fragmentation style emerged as the most influential parameter in most cases, being identified as the dominant factor in 224 out of 392 regressions (57%). This was followed by discorporation half-life, which was the most influential in 99 cases (25%). Notably, in 64 of these 99 cases, the receiving compartment was either Impacted Soil or Impacted Soil Surface, suggesting a consistent association between degradation processes and these terrestrial compartments. When evaluating the second most influential parameter, fragmentation timescale clearly dominated, appearing in 335 out of 392 cases (85%). Fragmentation style followed, being the second most influential in 57 cases (15%). See *Figure 8* for visual summary. This further reinforces the critical role of fragmentation dynamics in shaping microplastic size distributions, particularly under different environmental settings.

Figure 8: Distribution of the most and second-most influential model parameters across 392 regression subsets, based on standardized regression coefficients (β).

Comparison of UTOPIA Model Outputs to Observed Datasets

The following are results obtained from the individual analysis of each of the studies by comparing the overlay of the modeled data to observed dataset. The overlay comparisons

revealed strong consistency across several datasets, particularly those involving surface water and sediment samples.

For the Song et al. (2018) datasets (Sea Surface Fibers and Fragments), excellent model agreement was observed in both Ocean_Surface_Water and Coast_Surface_Water compartments. Fibers yielded R^2 values up to 0.85 and RMSE as low as 0.12, while fragments reached R^2 values up to 0.94 with RMSE around 0.18. The top-performing scenarios consistently involved low-density polymers (900 kg/m^3) and fragmentation style between 0.3 and 0.7.

The Enders et al. (2015) datasets also showed strong alignment, particularly for Sea Surface Fibers, with best-fit runs using 900 kg/m^3 plastics and FI values of 0.3–0.7 (R^2 up to 0.77, RMSE ~ 0.19). Sea Surface Fragments performed best with denser polymers ($1100\text{--}1500 \text{ kg/m}^3$), achieving slightly lower but still robust fits ($R^2 \sim 0.73$, RMSE $\sim 0.28\text{--}0.34$).

In the Isobe et al. (2014) Sea Surface All dataset, moderate fits were achieved across coastal and open-ocean compartments ($R^2 \sim 0.50\text{--}0.59$; RMSE $\sim 0.18\text{--}0.22$). The best overlays used 900 kg/m^3 plastics with FI = 0.3–0.7 and long discorporation half-life ($\text{thalf_deg} = 31600\text{--}100000$ days).

For Cai et al. (2018), top overlays for the Sea Surface All dataset were observed in Surface_Freshwater and marine compartments using 900 kg/m^3 polymers with FI values of 0.3–0.5. The best model runs achieved R^2 values up to 0.92 and RMSE as low as 0.17.

Among sediment datasets, the Imhof et al. (2016) Freshwater Sediments data produced good fits using intermediate- to high-density polymers ($1100\text{--}1500 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and FI = 0.3–0.5, consistent with small, fragmented particles. The Eo et al. (2019) Fragments in Sediment dataset showed high correlation ($R^2 \sim 0.84$) with FI = 1, indicating complete fragmentation. However, Fibers in Sediment from the same study showed poor fits ($R^2 < 0$), reflecting challenges in modeling fibrous MPs in sediment.

Lastly, Bergmann et al. (2017) Sea Sediment results demonstrated excellent model performance ($R^2 = 0.96$, RMSE = 0.13) with simulations involving high-density polymers ($1100\text{--}1500 \text{ kg/m}^3$) and complete fragmentation (FI = 1), matching observations of deep Arctic sediment accumulation.

In summary, the UTOPIA model was able to simulate observed microplastic size distributions across a wide range of environmental scenarios. The best model performance was achieved when the input parameters closely reflected environmentally plausible conditions, especially with respect to plastic density and fragmentation behavior. Both the statistical analyses and visual overlays support the model's ability to replicate empirical patterns under well-matched assumptions. These results lay the foundation for a more detailed interpretation and contextualization in the following discussion.

Discussion

Model Limitations and Structural Constraints

This study aimed to evaluate the UTOPIA model's ability to simulate observed microplastic size distributions and to reduce uncertainties in key input parameters related to fragmentation and degradation. While the model offers a robust framework for understanding microplastic fate and transport, several limitations in its current implementation must be considered when interpreting the results.

First, UTOPIA is currently parameterized only to describe the behavior of spherical particles, particularly in its treatment of settling and aggregation processes. However, the observed datasets include a range of shapes, notably fibers and fragments, which behave differently from spheres in terms of sinking rates and hydrodynamic drag in laboratory studies. Applying a sphere-based model to simulate fiber-dominated datasets may lead to biased representations, particularly in compartments such as sediments or deep waters where settling behavior becomes more influential (Kowalski et al., 2016).

Another notable limitation lies in the discretization of particle sizes. The model simulates five fixed size bins but only the three largest bins (50 μm , 500 μm , and 5000 μm) are in the range of available measurement data. Most observational studies report size distributions using a much finer resolution within that size range—often with 10 to 20 bins covering the reported size spectrum (Kooi & Koelmans, 2019). To compare these datasets, we had to interpolate model results, especially in the smaller size range, which adds uncertainty to the fitting process and may obscure key features of the empirical distributions.

Evaluating Model Performance Against Observed Distributions

Despite these limitations, the analysis carried out in this study reveals several important trends and insights into the UTOPIA model's behavior. By systematically testing over 21,000 parameter combinations across various emissions and receiving compartments, we identified two subsets of parameter combinations that provided strong agreement with observed microplastic size distributions. Importantly, these combinations were not just good statistical fits, but also aligned logically with known environmental processes, for example, matches involving low-density plastics and shallow compartments where we would reasonably expect buoyant microplastics to accumulate. This distinction between statistical fitness and environmental plausibility is critical, as the model can reproduce observed distributions with unrealistic assumptions, underscoring the need for scrutiny of input parameters.

Returning to the central goals of this thesis, one key aim was to evaluate the ability of the UTOPIA model to simulate observed microplastic size distributions across a range of environmental contexts. The results suggest that while UTOPIA can replicate observed patterns with a high degree of accuracy, this is conditional on the selection of environmentally plausible input parameters. For example, model outputs showed strong agreement with observed data from Song et al. (2018) and Enders et al. (2015), particularly in surface water compartments, when emissions involved low-density polymers (900 kg/m^3) and fragmentation styles representing more erosive processes ($\text{FI} = 0.3\text{--}0.5$). These parameter combinations yielded high R^2 values (up to 0.94) and low RMSE scores (as low as 0.12), indicating that under well-aligned assumptions, the model performs robustly.

However, not all observed datasets were captured with the same fidelity. In certain cases, such as the Eo et al. (2019) sediment fiber dataset, model overlays failed to reproduce observed distributions, possibly because the shape or behavior of microplastics deviated from the assumptions embedded in the model (e.g., spherical particles, pristine form). These mismatches highlight the importance of selecting model compartments and emission scenarios that closely reflect the sampling context. For instance, high-density microplastic from Bergmann et al. (2017) in Arctic deep-sea sediments were best replicated when emissions were traced from ocean surface layers through to sediment compartments using complete fragmentation and degradation schemes.

Overall, these results reinforce that UTOPIA's strength lies not just in its flexibility to simulate various scenarios, but in its reliance on parameter realism. The ability to achieve statistical agreement with observed data does not automatically validate a model run if the underlying assumptions are physically implausible. Thus, the comparison of modeled outputs to empirical datasets serves a dual purpose validating the model's structure and identifying combinations of input parameters that are both environmentally realistic and statistically robust.

Influence of Fragmentation and Degradation Parameters

The second aim was to reduce uncertainties surrounding the key input parameters related to fragmentation style, fragmentation timescale, and discorporation half-life. The regression-based analysis of standardized input parameters (Z scores) provides key insights into the relative importance of fragmentation and degradation dynamics in shaping model performance across diverse environmental contexts. Among the three parameters tested fragmentation style, fragmentation timescale, and discorporation half-life, fragmentation style consistently emerged as the most influential predictor of RMSE. This was evident in 57% of the 392 regression subsets, suggesting that how microplastics break down (i.e., whether fragmentation occurs explosively or erosively) has a dominant effect on the resulting size distributions and their match to observed data.

The significance of fragmentation style likely stems from its central role in determining the pace and pathway by which larger plastic particles disintegrate into smaller ones. Erosive fragmentation, represented by lower FI values, gradually sheds small fragments over time, whereas sequential fragmentation (higher FI values) leads to sudden generation of intermediate sizes. Since the model's outputs are highly sensitive to the shape of the size distribution, even subtle shifts in fragmentation dynamics can produce large differences in RMSE. This sensitivity helps explain why fragmentation style was not only frequently the strongest predictor but also rarely exhibited no correlation with RMSE (only 10% of cases).

Fragmentation timescale was also shown to be a highly relevant parameter. While it was the most dominant factor in fewer cases than fragmentation style, it consistently emerged as the second-most influential parameter in 85% of all subsets. This suggests that the duration over which fragmentation occurs independent of the fragmentation style, still plays a major role in shaping final size distributions and fate of the microplastic. Faster fragmentation timescales (i.e., lower values) tend to generate an abundance of smaller particles more quickly, which may improve model fits when the observed data which contains a strong skew toward smaller size bins (Cai et al. 2018).

Whereas discorporation half-life was found to be the least influential parameter overall, emerging as the most significant in only 25% of cases. However, its influence was not uniformly weak. In fact, a key pattern emerged in which discorporation half-life was most relevant when the receiving compartment was terrestrial, specifically Impacted Soil or Impacted Soil Surface. In 64 of the 99 subsets where discorporation half-life dominated, these two compartments were involved. This likely reflects the longer residence times and slower environmental dynamics in soil systems, where degradation processes may play a more significant role in altering microplastic abundance over time than in dynamic aquatic systems.

Collectively, these findings support the hypothesis that constraining fragmentation-related processes, both in style and timing, is crucial for improving model accuracy and reducing uncertainty. discorporation half-life, while important in certain compartments, generally exerted a weaker influence. This reinforces the need to prioritize the parameterization of fragmentation mechanisms when refining fate models like UTOPIA, especially given the current lack of empirical data on environmental fragmentation behavior. The results also highlight the importance of disaggregating model analysis by environmental context, as parameter influence is clearly compartment-dependent.

Insights from Best-Performing Parameter Combinations

In addition to the regression-based analysis, a focused review of the best-performing model runs, those with the lowest RMSE values and strongest overlays with observed distributions, provided further insight into how different parameter combinations influenced model performance. Among the top 20 runs for each dataset, a clear pattern emerged with respect to plastic density and the associated fragmentation parameters.

Lower-density plastics (900 kg/m^3) were most often paired with lower fragmentation style values ($\text{FI} = 0.3$ or 0.5), consistent with erosive fragmentation processes. These scenarios also tended to involve shorter fragmentation timescales, indicating that surface abrasion and progressive breakdown may dominate the fate of buoyant, low-density microplastics in surface environments. This trend aligns with experimental observations and field reports suggesting that lighter plastics remain suspended longer and undergo gradual surface erosion from physical and biological forces (Kowalski et al., 2016; Andrady, 2011).

A notable trend emerged for high-density plastics ($1100\text{--}1500 \text{ kg/m}^3$), which were more commonly associated with higher fragmentation style values ($\text{FI} = 0.7$ or 1.0), pointing toward more sequential or explosive fragmentation behaviors. These combinations were also paired with longer fragmentation timescales. This suggests that denser plastics may persist in larger forms for extended periods before undergoing sudden breakage. One possible explanation lies in the material composition of these plastics. High-density polymers often incorporate a larger proportion of chemical additives to enhance durability and performance. As these materials weather over time, especially under UV radiation and oxidative stress, they tend to undergo internal changes such as increased crystallinity. This internal degradation weakens the polymer structure, causing it to become brittle and eventually fragment in a more abrupt, sequential manner (Andrady, 2011; Singh & Sharma, 2008). In contrast, low-density plastics, which typically contain fewer additives, appear more susceptible to gradual, surface-level erosion. This aligns with their frequent association in the model results with lower FI values ($0.3\text{--}0.5$) and shorter fragmentation timescales traits indicative of a more continuous, erosive fragmentation pathway. These interpretations are consistent with known degradation

mechanisms and provide a plausible mechanistic explanation for the model's parameter sensitivities.

Discorporation half-life ($t_{\text{half_deg}}$) did not exhibit a consistent or dominant influence in the top-performing runs. While it was included in the parameter sweeps and regression analysis, its contribution to model fit appeared highly context-dependent and did not follow a clear trend across density classes or compartments. This further supports the conclusion from the regression analysis that degradation may play a secondary role relative to fragmentation style and timing in determining the resulting size distributions under the scenarios explored here.

Practical Recommendations for Model Users and Future Directions

Crucially, the patterns observed across these top-performing scenarios not only help validate the model's underlying structure but also offer practical value for future applications. Specifically, they may serve as a reference for default parameter selection in cases where users of the UTOPIA model lack empirical input data. By identifying parameter combinations that yield both statistically robust fits and environmentally plausible behavior, this study provides a preliminary framework for simulating the fate of generic microplastic types under varied environmental conditions. Also, in situations where empirical data are lacking, this study provides a basis for recommending default parameter combinations. For example, if the user is simulating emissions of low-density plastics (e.g., 900 kg/m³), they can default to using lower FI values (0.3–0.5), representing erosive fragmentation, along with shorter fragmentation timescales. In contrast, for high-density plastics (e.g., 1100–1500 kg/m³), higher FI values (0.7–1.0), indicative of sequential fragmentation, and longer fragmentation timescales are more appropriate. These recommendations, derived from scenarios with both strong model fit and environmental plausibility, can help users make informed assumptions when empirical inputs are unavailable.

These trends reinforce the hypothesis that observed environmental size distributions can help constrain fragmentation-related parameters in fate models, especially when interpreted in the context of polymer density and environmental setting. They also highlight the potential of models like UTOPIA to serve not just as predictive tools, but as structured platforms for testing and refining assumptions about microplastic behavior in the absence of detailed empirical data.

In summary, this study demonstrates that while the UTOPIA model is a powerful tool for simulating microplastic fate, its accuracy and interpretability are highly dependent on thoughtful parameter selection and alignment with environmental context. By combining rigorous scenario testing with comparison to observed datasets, this work not only evaluates the model's predictive performance but also provides new guidance on how to reduce uncertainty in key input parameters. These findings emphasize the importance of continued empirical research on fragmentation and degradation dynamics and reinforce the value of models like UTOPIA in synthesizing existing knowledge, identifying data gaps, and supporting informed environmental decision-making on microplastic pollution.

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Supplementary Materials

1. Supplementary File S1: Processed UTOPIA Model Output Dataset – Contains the filtered simulation outputs used for evaluating model fit metrics across all scenarios. Includes overlay data for each iteration. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15477501](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15477501)
2. Supplementary File S2: Top 20 Best-Fit Scenarios Analysis – Lists the top-performing parameter combinations from each dataset based on lowest RMSE values. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15477565](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15477565)
3. Supplementary File S3: Z-score Standardization and Regression Analysis Dataset – Contains standardized parameter values, RMSE, and calculated regression coefficients across 392 subsets. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15477521](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15477521)